

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

OPERATION ACOLHIDA AND THE MAIN CHALLENGES IN INTERAGENCY COOPERATION.

Ana Luiza Bravo e Paiva

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Policy Statement

This policy brief delves into the primary challenges within interagency cooperation as manifested in Operation Acolhida. Before delineating the chief constraints witnessed in this domain, an effort is made to establish a connection between the inception of interagency doctrine in Brazil and systemic transformations, drawing insights from pertinent literature on interagency affairs. Ultimately, recommendations and opportunities for improvement are proffered in response to the identified issues.

Background

In the contemporary context, there is an observable expansion in the scope of responsibilities entrusted to the Armed Forces. In addition to their traditional roles in safeguarding states' sovereignty and territorial integrity, military forces have been regularly deployed in domestic security, assistance in natural disasters, and humanitarian crises (Weiss, 2011; Cook, 2021). According to specialized literature, such changes in military roles and missions [1] are linked to the new security dynamics observed in the post-Cold War era. In this regard, faced with the need to address increasingly complex issues, there is a growing concern to enhance the relationship between state actors (including their diverse agencies), civil society, and the private sector.

During the 1990s and 2000s, the debate on interagency cooperation gained considerable prominence in public policy studies. Enthusiasts of this perspective argue that more significant interaction among the public and, in some cases, private organizations could lead to the development of more effective and efficient public policies. This, they contend, would allow for the rational use of resources and create an innovative environment conducive to the rapid development of holistic responses to the challenges faced by such organizations (Bardach, 1998, 2001). From the public administration and governance perspective, many states and international organizations have shown interest in promoting reforms, facilitating more significant interaction among the stakeholders involved in public policy development.

Concerning military affairs, there is an incorporation of debates about the new roles and missions of the Armed Forces associated with concerns in interagency relations.

In this regard, some doctrinal adaptations have been undertaken. In Brazil, throughout its history, despite the repeated involvement of the Armed Forces in domestic affairs, the interagency doctrine was developed in the context of significant events such as the World Cup and the Olympics. The participation of Brazilian military personnel in United Nations peacekeeping operations is also recognized as one of the factors contributing to the doctrinal update, given that operations conducted by international organizations entail a vital civil-military coordination [2] component.

As we will see throughout this text, Operation Acolhida is one of Brazil's primary ongoing interagency operations. The complexity of this operation arises from the quantitative and qualitative variety of organizations and processes engendered in the governance structure of the operation. It is from this multiplicity that the challenges presented here derive.

Findings

In March 2018, faced with the humanitarian challenges posed by a sharp increase in Venezuelan immigration at the northern border (Mendes & Fernandes, 2021, p. 224), the Brazilian government acknowledged the region's vulnerability (Brazil, 2018). On that occasion, an Interministerial Committee was established to assist and protect those vulnerable individuals from Venezuela. Although Operation Acolhida is coordinated by the Civil House Chief, given the Amazon region's logistical challenges, the Ministry of Defense and the Armed Forces played a significant role in this operation.

As a result, the Brazilian Army took the lead in a task force aimed at systematizing the actions of the different actors involved in the mentioned operation. The activities carried out by Operation Acolhida are based on three pillars: 1) border management, 2) sheltering, and 3) internalization of immigrants. According to the Military Doctrine of Defense of Brazil, Operation Acolhida is a humanitarian, joint, and interagency operation.

The complexity inherent in Acolhida involves a series of normative-legal requirements, international assignments, surveillance, and logistical resources. Recognizing the vulnerability of refugees occurred through Presidential Decree No. 9285, dated March 15, 2018, and establishing the Federal Emergency Assistance Committee.

In the city of Pacaraima (in the state of Roraima - RR), various structures operate with coordination between Governmental Organizations (GO), International Organizations (IO), and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO): Reception and Identification Post, Internalization and Screening Post, Advanced Service Post, Pacaraima Base, Janokoida Shelter, and BV-8 Accommodation. Operation Acolhida is interministerial and dependent on systems and subsystems of cooperation between agencies; it involves coordination between the Chief of Staff of the President and an Executive Secretariat of the Federal Committee linked to the Ministry of Defense.

Currently, in Boa Vista, the capital of the state of Roraima, there are ten shelters, an Internalization Area (Rondon II), the Boa Vista Base, and an Internalization and Screening Post. There is also a Reception and Support Station with three structures located in an area adjacent to the bus station: luggage storage, information points, chemical toilets, overnight area, shower area, children's space, and laundry, as well as an area for distribution and consumption of donated meals (Oliveira, 2018).

In the city of Manaus (in the state of Amazonas - AM), there is a Transit Accommodation, which acts as a hub in the internalization process, a Support Base, a Reception and Support Post, and an Internalization and Screening Post. Regarding derived policies, Ministerial Directive No. 03/2018/MD characterizes the humanitarian aid operation, while Ministerial Directive No. 04/2018/MD focuses on parameters and responsibilities for executing Reception and Control Operations. In parallel with Operation Acolhida, the Control Operation was instituted to support the Federal Police in immigration control and prevent transborder crimes in the region with the highest influx of immigrants.

The Roraima Humanitarian Logistics Task Force is responsible for planning and executing Operation Acolhida, collaborating with federal, state, and municipal governments. With a contingent of approximately 200 military personnel, formed by the three Forces (Army et al.), the Task Force carries out general actions such as reception, identification, screening, immunization, sheltering, and internalization of underserved Venezuelans.

The classification as a joint and interagency humanitarian operation allowed the planning and conduct of actions, creating an Interagency Staff, which advises the Operational Coordinator of the Task Force and keeps them continuously informed about the unfolding events and results of the actions.

The complexity of Operation Acolhida can be observed through some numbers: 1) the number of people they are dealing with, 2) the quantity and types of agencies involved, and 3) the political frameworks for the entire operation. The figures below show the volume of assisted immigrants as well as the number of agencies involved in the operation:

FIGURE 1: Temporary Residence Requests and Refuge Requests in Operation Acolhida (January 2017 to July 2023)

Source: Operation Acolhida Official Website

FIGURE 2: Agencies involved in Operation Acolhida

Source: Brazilian Ministry of Defense (2020).

While the Brazilian government and international agencies consider Operation Acolhida a milestone in civilian-military relations, there are opportunities for improvement in interagency cooperation. After conducting field research in Boa Vista and Pacaraima, Renata Costa (2020) pointed out that although the Brazilian government sought to develop a horizontal governance structure among actors, in practice, what was observed was the assignment of leadership to the military component.

For the author, such asymmetry in the decision-making environment contributes little to developing trust among the actors. In operations of this nature, as highlighted by specialized literature, trust is a central element in achieving effectiveness and efficiency. After all, as each agency deals with a specific volume of sensitive information, the exchange of this information is only established in environments where there is trust among the actors.

Another aspect Costa emphasizes in her evaluation is the issue of the turnover of military contingents involved in Operation Acolhida. According to the author, the fact that military personnel are rotated every four months compromises the effectiveness and efficiency of the operation, as it directly interferes with the flow of information and knowledge management.

The author also suggests that differences in organizational culture among agencies could be a potential source of conflict. According to her accounts, even though it is an interagency operation, the organizations involved in Acolhida showed low flexibility and adaptability in the operational context. For Renata Costa, there would be a tendency toward centralization and hierarchy, primarily derived from the organizational culture of the Armed Forces.

Recommendations

Based on the diagnosis conducted throughout the text, for the purpose of improving interagency cooperation in the context of Operation Acolhida, the following needs are identified:

- (i) The development of more flexible doctrines and greater adaptability in the interagency operational context.
- (ii) The revision and extension of the rotation period practiced by military contingents involved in Operation Acolhida.
- (iii) The creation of formal and permanent channels for exchanging information between agencies.
- (iv) The enhancement of evaluation indicators for interagency operations to identify key obstacles and enable the incorporation of potential improvement opportunities.

Conclusions

The text presented a comprehensive analysis of the expansion of the roles of the Armed Forces in the contemporary scenario, highlighting the growing importance of interagency operations, with a focus on Operation Acolhida in Brazil. The evolution of military roles, associated with changes in security dynamics post-Cold War, reflects the need for broader approaches to deal with complex challenges, resulting in the search for better cooperation between different state actors, civil society, and the private sector.

The results of Operation Acolhida, in the face of humanitarian challenges posed by Venezuelan immigration, demonstrate the relevance of the Armed Forces in coordinating interagency actions. However, the text points to significant challenges,

such as leadership asymmetry, contingent turnover, lack of formal channels for information exchange, and the cultural rigidity of the agencies involved.

The importance of trust as a central element for the effectiveness and efficiency of interagency operations was emphasized. Additionally, it highlights that organizational rigidity, particularly in the Armed Forces, can create obstacles to the flexibility and adaptation necessary in operational contexts involving multiple actors.

In this context, the recommendations to enhance interagency cooperation in Operation Acolhida include the need for more flexible doctrines, a review of the rotation period for military contingents, the creation of permanent channels for information exchange, and the enhancement of evaluation indicators. These suggestions aim to overcome the identified challenges, promoting a more effective and adaptable approach to interagency operations in the future.

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Ana Luiza Bravo e Paiva (InterAgency Institute; Brazilian Army Command and General Staff College): Ph.D. in Comparative History from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro. Faculty member in the Postgraduate Program in Military Sciences at the Brazilian Army Command and General Staff College.

[1] Notwithstanding the existence of studies highlighting the dangers of the unrestricted use of the military component in the domestic environment, this text assumes that, in contemporary times, the Armed Forces have taken on an increasing number of responsibilities, predominantly of a humanitarian and interagency nature.

[2] For further information on Civil-Military Coordination within the United Nations Peacekeeping Operations, please visit the website: <https://peacekeepingresourcehub.un.org/en/training/stm/cimic>

Ana Luiza Bravo e Paiva (InterAgency Institute; ECEME): Ph.D. and MPhil in Comparative History (UFRJ), Assistant Professor at the Brazilian Army Command and Staff College, and former Lecturer at DGEI/IRID (UFRJ).

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<https://interagency.institute/>
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